

R scripts

Microbiome response to stress

#Statistical tools Primarily PERMANOVA, alpha diversity and the CLR transformation.

```
library(vegan)      #install.packages("vegan")
```

```
library(iNEXT)      #install.packages("iNEXT")
```

```
library(Tjazi)      #devtools::install_github("thomazbastiaanssen/Tjazi")
```

```
library(lme4)
```

```
library(lmerTest)
```

#Data Wrangling

```
library(tidyverse)      #install.packages("tidyverse")
```

```
library(knitr)      #install.packages("knitr")
```

```
library(waldo)      #install.packages("waldo")
```

#Plotting

```
library(ggplot2)      #install.packages("ggplot2")
```

```
library(ggforce)      #install.packages("ggforce")
```

```
library(patchwork)      #install.packages("patchwork")
```

```
library(ggbeeswarm)      #install.packages("ggbeeswarm")
```

```
library(metafolio)      #install.packages("metafolio")
```

#Disable strings automatically being read in as factors to avoid unintuitive behaviour.

```
options(stringsAsFactors = F)
```

#Set a seed for the purposes of reproducibility in this document.

```
set.seed(1)
```

#Load in the genus level count table and the metadata file.

```
counts <-
```

```
read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/veronica_fig1/StressVeronicaBacteriome/OtuTable", sep = ",",  
row.names = 1, header = T)
```

```
tl <-  
read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/veronica_fig1/StressVeronicaBacteriome/Table_TAXA", sep =  
",", row.names = 1, header = T)  
tl <- tl[order(tl$OTU),]
```

```
metadata <-  
read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/veronica_fig1/StressVeronicaBacteriome/Sample_data", sep =  
",", row.names = 1, header = T)
```

```
counts$OTUID = paste(tl$Family, tl$Genus, tl$OTU, sep = "_")
```

```
counts = counts %>%  
  filter(!str_detect(OTUID, "Unclassified")) %>%  
  column_to_rownames("OTUID")
```

```
metadata <- metadata[metadata$Condition.1 != "T0",]  
#Fork off your count data so that you always have an untouched version handy.  
genus <- counts[,metadata$...1]
```

```
#make sure our count data is all numbers  
genus <- apply(genus,c(1,2),function(x) as.numeric(as.character(x)))
```

```
#Remove features with prevalence < 10% in two steps:  
#First, determine how often every feature is absent in a sample  
n_zeroes <- rowSums(genus == 0)
```

```
#Then, remove features that are absent in more than your threshold (90% in this case).  
genus <- genus[n_zeroes <= round(ncol(genus) * 0.90),]
```

```
#Perform a CLR transformation  
genus.exp <- clr_c(genus)
```

```

# Alpha diversity -----

alpha_diversity = get_asymptotic_alpha(species = counts[,metadata$...1], verbose = FALSE)

#Add metadata for plotting and stats. Make sure the count table and metadata match up!
#Add relevant information from the metadata
alpha_diversity$ID      = metadata$...1
alpha_diversity$Source  = factor(metadata$Type, levels = c("Faecal Bacteriome", "Caecal
Bacteriome"))
alpha_diversity$Legend  = metadata$Treatment

#Plot alpha diversity all at once using pipes
a_bc <- alpha_diversity %>%

#Wrangle the data to long format for easy plotting
pivot_longer(!c(ID, Source, Legend)) %>%
filter(Source == "Faecal Bacteriome") %>%

#Pipe it all directly into ggplot2
ggplot(aes(x   = Legend,
           y   = value,
           fill = Legend,
           group = Legend)) +
geom_boxplot(alpha = 1/2, coef = 100) +
geom_dotplot(dotsize = 3, binaxis = "y", stackdir = "center") +
facet_wrap(~name, scales = "free", nrow = 3) + theme_bw() +
scale_colour_manual(values = c("Control" = "#377eb8", "Stress" = "#e41a1c")) +
scale_fill_manual(values = c("Control" = "#377eb8", "Stress" = "#e41a1c")) +
ylab("") + xlab("")

a_bf <- alpha_diversity %>%

```

```

#Wrangle the data to long format for easy plotting
pivot_longer(!c(ID, Source, Legend)) %>%
filter(Source != "Faecal Bacteriome") %>%

#Pipe it all directly into ggplot2
ggplot(aes(x = Legend,
           y = value,
           fill = Legend,
           group = Legend)) +
geom_boxplot(alpha = 1/2, coef = 100) +
geom_dotplot(dotsize = 3, binaxis = "y", stackdir = "center") +
facet_wrap(~name, scales = "free", nrow = 3) + theme_bw() +
scale_colour_manual(values = c("Control" = "#377eb8", "Stress" = "#e41a1c")) +
scale_fill_manual(values = c("Control" = "#377eb8", "Stress" = "#e41a1c")) +
ylab("") + xlab("")

```

Beta Diversity -----

#Apply the base R principal component analysis function on our CLR-transformed data.

```
data.a.pca <- prcomp(t(genus.exp))
```

#Extract the amount of variance the first four components explain for plotting.

```
pc1 <- round(data.a.pca$sdev[1]^2/sum(data.a.pca$sdev^2),4) * 100
```

```
pc2 <- round(data.a.pca$sdev[2]^2/sum(data.a.pca$sdev^2),4) * 100
```

```
pc3 <- round(data.a.pca$sdev[3]^2/sum(data.a.pca$sdev^2),4) * 100
```

```
pc4 <- round(data.a.pca$sdev[4]^2/sum(data.a.pca$sdev^2),4) * 100
```

#Extract the scores for every sample for the first four components for plotting.

```

pca = data.frame(PC1 = data.a.pca$x[,1],
                PC2 = data.a.pca$x[,2],
                PC3 = data.a.pca$x[,3],
                PC4 = data.a.pca$x[,4])

#Add relevant information from the metadata
pca$ID          = metadata$...1
pca$Source      = factor(metadata$Type, levels = c("Faecal Bacteriome", "Caecal Bacteriome"))
pca$Legend      = metadata$Treatment

#First, the main plot. Plot the first two components of the PCA
pb_f = pca %>%
  filter(Source == "Faecal Bacteriome") %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = PC1,
             y   = PC2,
             fill = Legend,
             colour = Legend,
             group = Legend)) +

#Create the points and ellipses
  geom_point(size=3, col = "black", shape = 21) +
  stat_ellipse(geom = "polygon", alpha = 1/4) +

#Adjust appearance
  facet_wrap(~Source) +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(override.aes = list(shape = c(21)))) +
  scale_colour_manual(values = c("Control" = "#377eb8", "Stress" = "#e41a1c")) +
  scale_fill_manual(values = c("Control" = "#377eb8", "Stress" = "#e41a1c")) +
  #Adjust labels
  xlab(paste("PC1: ", pc1, "%", sep="")) +

```

```
ylab(paste("PC2: ", pc2, "%", sep="")) +  
theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") +  
theme(text = element_text(size = 14))
```

pb_f

```
#First, the main plot. Plot the first two components of the PCA
```

```
pb_c = pca %>%  
  filter(Source == "Caecal Bacteriome") %>%  
  ggplot(aes(x = PC1,  
            y   = PC2,  
            fill = Legend,  
            colour = Legend,  
            group = Legend)) +
```

```
#Create the points and ellipses
```

```
geom_point(size=3, col = "black", shape = 21) +  
stat_ellipse(geom = "polygon", alpha = 1/4) +
```

```
#Adjust appearance
```

```
facet_wrap(~Source) +  
guides(fill = guide_legend(override.aes = list(shape = c(21)))) +  
scale_colour_manual(values = c("Control" = "#377eb8", "Stress" = "#e41a1c")) +  
scale_fill_manual(values = c("Control" = "#377eb8", "Stress" = "#e41a1c")) +
```

```
#Adjust labels
```

```
xlab(paste("PC1: ", pc1, "%", sep="")) +  
ylab(paste("PC2: ", pc2, "%", sep="")) +  
theme_bw() + theme(legend.position = "none") +  
theme(text = element_text(size = 14))
```

pb_c

```

#Fork off from the untransformed counts table
bargenus <- counts[,metadata$...1]

#Make into relative abundance
bargenus <- apply(bargenus, 2, function(i) i/sum(i))

#Define a cutoff for rare taxa in several steps:
#first, determine the max % abundance every feature ever shows up at
maxabundances <- apply(bargenus, 1, max)

#Meanwhile, transpose the count table for future wrangling.
bargenus <- data.frame(t(bargenus))

#For every sample, sum up all rare taxa (< 1% at their highest in this case)
bargenus`Rare Taxa` <- rowSums(bargenus[,maxabundances < 0.05], na.rm = TRUE)

#Remove the individual rare taxa now that they're summed up
bargenus = bargenus[,c(maxabundances > 0.05, T) ] #`T` to include the `Rare Taxa`.

#Prepare the data for ggplot by adding in metadata here
bargenus$ID = metadata$...1
bargenus$Source = factor(metadata$Type, levels = c("Faecal Bacteriome", "Caecal Bacteriome",
"Faecal Virome"))
bargenus$Legend = metadata$Treatment

#Wrangle the data to long format for easy plotting
barlong = bargenus %>%
  pivot_longer(!c(ID, Source, Legend), names_to = c("Microbe"), values_to = "value") %>%
  mutate(Microbe = str_replace(Microbe, ".*_or_", ""))

#Change the colour for the rare taxa to gray to make them stand out

```

```

cols = metafolio::gg_color_hue(length(unique(barlong$Microbe)))
cols[unique(barlong$Microbe)=="Rare Taxa"]="dark gray"

#Create the stacked barplots using ggplot2
bp_bf <- barlong %>%
  filter(Source == "Faecal Bacteriome") %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = ID, y = value, fill = Microbe)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", col = "black", size = .2, width = 1) +
  facet_row(~Source + Legend, scales = "free_x") +
  #Adjust layout and appearance
  scale_fill_manual(values = cols, labels = unique(sub(".*ales_", "", barlong$Microbe))) +
  scale_y_continuous(expand = c(0, 0)) +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(ncol = 1, keyheight = 1, title = "Legend")) +
  theme_bw() + xlab("") + ylab("Proportion") +
  theme(text = element_text(size = 14), axis.text.x = element_blank(), legend.position = "none")

bp_bc <- barlong %>%
  filter(Source == "Caecal Bacteriome") %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = ID, y = value, fill = Microbe)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", col = "black", size = .2, width = 1) +
  facet_row(~Source + Legend, scales = "free_x") +
  #Adjust layout and appearance
  scale_fill_manual(values = cols, labels = unique(sub(".*ales_", "", barlong$Microbe))) +
  scale_y_continuous(expand = c(0, 0)) +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(ncol = 1, keyheight = 1, title = "Legend")) +
  theme_bw() + xlab("") + ylab("Proportion") +
  theme(text = element_text(size = 14), axis.text.x = element_blank(), legend.position = "none")

#Load in the genus level count table and the metadata file.

```

```

counts <-
read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/veronica_fig1/StressVeronicaVirome/ViromeOTUtable", sep =
",", row.names = 1, header = T)

metadata <-
read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/veronica_fig1/StressVeronicaVirome/Sample_data.csv", sep =
",", header = T)

metadata <- metadata[metadata$Time != "T0",]
#Fork off your count data so that you always have an untouched version handy.
genus <- counts[,metadata$X]

#make sure our count data is all numbers
genus <- apply(genus,c(1,2),function(x) as.numeric(as.character(x)))

#Remove features with prevalence < 10% in two steps:
#First, determine how often every feature is absent in a sample
n_zeroes <- rowSums(genus == 0)

#Then, remove features that are absent in more than your threshold (90% in this case).
genus <- genus[n_zeroes <= round(ncol(genus) * 0.90),]

#Perform a CLR transformation
genus.exp <- clr_c(genus)

dim(genus.exp)
# Alpha diversity -----
vgenus <- counts[,metadata$X]
row.names(vgenus) <- counts$Viral.contig
alpha_diversity = get_asymptotic_alpha(species = vgenus, verbose = FALSE)

#Add metadata for plotting and stats. Make sure the count table and metadata match up!

```

```

#Add relevant information from the metadata
alpha_diversity$ID          = metadata$X
alpha_diversity$Source      = factor("Faecal Virome", levels = c("Faecal Bacteriome", "Caecal
Bacteriome", "Faecal Virome"))
alpha_diversity$Legend      = metadata$Treatment

```

```

#Plot alpha diversity all at once using pipes

```

```

a_v <- alpha_diversity %>%

```

```

#Wrangle the data to long format for easy plotting

```

```

pivot_longer(!c(ID, Source, Legend)) %>%

```

```

#Pipe it all directly into ggplot2

```

```

ggplot(aes(x    = Legend,
           y    = value,
           fill = Legend,
           group = Legend)) +
geom_boxplot(alpha = 1/2, coef = 100) +
geom_dotplot(dotsize = 3, binaxis = "y", stackdir = "center") +
facet_wrap(~name, scales = "free_y", ncol = 1) +
theme_bw() +
scale_colour_manual(values = c("Control" = "#377eb8", "Stress" = "#e41a1c")) +
scale_fill_manual(values = c("Control" = "#377eb8", "Stress" = "#e41a1c")) +
ylab("") + xlab("")

```

```

# Beta Diversity -----

```

```

#Apply the base R principal component analysis function on our CLR-transformed data.

```

```

data.a.pca <- prcomp(t(genus.exp))

```

```

#Extract the amount of variance the first four components explain for plotting.

```

```

pc1 <- round(data.a.pca$sdev[1]^2/sum(data.a.pca$sdev^2),4) * 100
pc2 <- round(data.a.pca$sdev[2]^2/sum(data.a.pca$sdev^2),4) * 100
pc3 <- round(data.a.pca$sdev[3]^2/sum(data.a.pca$sdev^2),4) * 100
pc4 <- round(data.a.pca$sdev[4]^2/sum(data.a.pca$sdev^2),4) * 100

#Extract the scores for every sample for the first four components for plotting.
pca = data.frame(PC1 = data.a.pca$x[,1],
                PC2 = data.a.pca$x[,2],
                PC3 = data.a.pca$x[,3],
                PC4 = data.a.pca$x[,4])

#Add relevant information from the metadata
pca$ID          = metadata$X
pca$Source      = metadata$Type
pca$Legend      = metadata$Treatment
pca$Type        = "Faecal Virome"

#First, the main plot. Plot the first two components of the PCA
pv = ggplot(pca,
            aes(x = PC1,
                y = PC2,
                fill = Legend,
                colour = Legend)) +

#Create the points and ellipses
geom_point(size=3, col = "black", shape = 21) +
ggforce::geom_mark_ellipse(alpha = 1/4) +

#Adjust appearance
facet_wrap(~Type)+

```

```

guides(fill = guide_legend(override.aes = list(shape = c(21)))) +
scale_colour_manual(values = c("Control" = "#377eb8", "Stress" = "#e41a1c")) +
scale_fill_manual(values = c("Control" = "#377eb8", "Stress" = "#e41a1c")) +
scale_y_continuous(expand = c(1/4, 1/4)) +
scale_x_continuous(expand = c(1/4, 1/4)) +

#Adjust labels
xlab(paste("PC1: ", pc1, "%", sep="")) +
ylab(paste("PC2: ", pc2, "%", sep="")) +
theme_bw() +
theme(text = element_text(size = 14))

#Fork off from the untransformed counts table
bargenus <- counts[,metadata$X]
row.names(bargenus) <- counts$Viral.contig

#Make into relative abundance
bargenus <- apply(bargenus, 2, function(i) i/sum(i))

#Define a cutoff for rare taxa in several steps:
#first, determine the max % abundance every feature ever shows up at
maxabundances <- apply(bargenus, 1, max)

#Meanwhile, transpose the count table for future wrangling.
bargenus <- data.frame(t(bargenus))

#For every sample, sum up all rare taxa (< 1% at their highest in this case)
bargenus$`Rare Taxa` <- rowSums(bargenus[,maxabundances < 0.05], na.rm = TRUE)

#Remove the individual rare taxa now that they're summed up
bargenus = bargenus[,c(maxabundances > 0.05, T) ] #`T` to include the `Rare Taxa`.

```

```

#Prepare the data for ggplot by adding in metadata here
bargenus$ID          = metadata$X
bargenus$Source      = "Faecal Virome"
bargenus$Legend      = metadata$Treatment

#Wrangle the data to long format for easy plotting
barlong = bargenus %>%
  pivot_longer(!c(ID, Legend, Source), names_to = c("Microbe"), values_to = "value") %>%
  mutate(Microbe = str_replace(Microbe, ".*_or_", ""))

#Change the colour for the rare taxa to gray to make them stand out
cols = metafolio::gg_color_hue(length(unique(barlong$Microbe)))
cols[unique(barlong$Microbe)=="Rare Taxa"]="dark gray"

#Create the stacked barplots using ggplot2
bp_v <- barlong %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = ID, y = value, fill = Microbe)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", col = "black", size = .2, width = 1) +
  facet_row(~Source + Legend, scales = "free_x") +
  #Adjust layout and appearance
  scale_fill_manual(values = cols, labels = unique(sub(".*ales_", "", barlong$Microbe))) +
  scale_y_continuous(expand = c(0, 0)) +
  guides(fill = guide_legend(ncol = 1, keyheight = 1, title = "Legend")) +
  theme_bw() + xlab("") + ylab("Proportion") +
  theme(text = element_text(size = 14), axis.text.x = element_blank(), legend.position = "none")

pcas = pb_f + pb_c + pv + plot_layout(guides = 'collect')

stacks = bp_bf + bp_bc + bp_v

```

```
alpha = a_bc + a_bf + a_v & theme(text = element_text(size = 14), legend.position = "none")
```

```
pcas / stacks / alpha +  
  plot_layout(heights = c(1, 1, 2), guides = 'collect') +  
  plot_annotation(tag_levels = "a")
```

Faecal virome transplant microbiome restoration

```
library(tidyverse)
```

```
library(metacal)
```

```
library(Tjazi)
```

```
reverselog_trans <- function(base = exp(1)) {  
  trans <- function(x) -log(x, base)  
  inv <- function(x) base^(-x)  
  scales::trans_new(paste0("reverselog-", format(base)), trans, inv,  
    scales::log_breaks(base = base),  
    domain = c(1e-100, Inf))  
}
```

```
imp_const <- function (vec)  
{  
  if(min(vec) == 0){  
    DL = min(vec[vec != 0])  
  
    vec[vec == 0] = 0.65 * DL  
  }  
  return(vec)  
}
```

```

counts <- read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/recalibration/species.tsv", row.names = 1)
metadata <- read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/recalibration/recal_metadata.csv", sep = ",", header
= T)
metadata = metadata[order(metadata$Proposed_mouse_ID),]

# counts <- read.delim("/data/rawdata/thomaz/Nate/recalibration/species.tsv", row.names = 1)
# metadata <- read.delim("/data/rawdata/thomaz/Nate/recalibration/recal_metadata.csv", sep = ",", header
= T)

row.names(counts) <- counts$Name
counts = counts[,-94]

counts <- counts[!row.names(counts) %in% c("Cutibacterium acnes", "Imtechella halotolerans"
,"Bifidobacterium pseudolongum","Sebaldella termitidis", "Eggerthella lenta" ),]

species <- counts[,metadata$Full_ID]
species <- apply(species,c(1,2),function(x) as.numeric(as.character(x)))
species <- species[apply(species <= 5, 1, sum) <= (ncol(species) * 0.00 ), ]

species = apply(species, 2, imp_const)

species = apply(species, 2, function(x){x/sum(x)})

s1 = species[,metadata$calib_batch == "baseline"]
s2 = read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/recalibration/observed.cal_plate2.csv", sep = ",",
row.names = 1)
s3 = read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/recalibration/observed.cal_plate3.csv", sep = ",",
row.names = 1)
s4 = read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/recalibration/observed.cal_plate4.csv", sep = ",",
row.names = 1)
s5 = read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/recalibration/observed.cal_plate5.csv", sep = ",",
row.names = 1)

```

```
sr = species[,metadata$plate == "platercon" & metadata$calib_batch != "baseline"]
```

```
row.names(s1)
```

```
dim(s3)
```

```
sp_recal = do.call(cbind, list(s1, s2, s3, s4, s5, sr  
    ))
```

```
sp_recal = sp_recal[,metadata$post_recal_name]
```

```
metadata = metadata[!c(metadata$plate == "platercon" & metadata$calib_batch != "baseline"),]
```

```
metadata = metadata[!metadata$Proposed_mouse_ID %in% c("6", "7", "11"),]
```

```
metadata = metadata[metadata$Contrasts != "hkFVT",]
```

```
#metadata = metadata[metadata$Timepoint == "Post",]
```

```
dim(sp_recal)
```

```
#write.csv(sp_recal, "~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/recalibration/recalibrated_species_count_table.csv")
```

```
sp_recal = sp_recal[,metadata$post_recal_name]
```

```
waldo::compare(sort(colnames(sp_recal)), sort(metadata$post_recal_name))
```

```
#sp_recal <- genefilter::varFilter(as.matrix(sp_recal), var.cutoff = 1/2)
```

```
species.exp = clr_c(sp_recal)
```

```
data.a.pca <- prcomp(t(species.exp))
```

```
pc1 <- round(data.a.pca$sdev[1]^2/sum(data.a.pca$sdev^2),4) *100
```

```
pc2 <- round(data.a.pca$sdev[2]^2/sum(data.a.pca$sdev^2),4) *100
```

```
pc3 <- round(data.a.pca$sdev[3]^2/sum(data.a.pca$sdev^2),4) *100
```

```
pc4 <- round(data.a.pca$sdev[4]^2/sum(data.a.pca$sdev^2),4) *100
```

```
pca = data.frame(PC1 = data.a.pca$x[,1],
```

```
          PC2 = data.a.pca$x[,2],
```

```
          PC3 = data.a.pca$x[,3],
```

```
          PC4 = data.a.pca$x[,4])
```

```
#metadata = metadata[metadata$plate != "platercon",]
```

```
pca$ID      = metadata$OG_name
```

```
pca$plate   = metadata$plate
```

```
pca$mouse_ID = metadata$Proposed_mouse_ID
```

```
pca$Stress  = metadata$Stress
```

```
pca$FVT     = metadata$FVT
```

```
pca$Legend  = paste(metadata$Stress, metadata$FVT)
```

```
pca$Timepoint = metadata$Timepoint
```

```
pca %>%
```

```
  #filter(Study == "APC085") %>%
```

```
  ggplot(aes(x = PC1,
```

```
          y = PC2,
```

```
          fill = plate,
```

```
          group = mouse_ID,
```

```
          label = mouse_ID
```

```

)) +
geom_line(size = sqrt(2), col = "black") +
geom_line(size = 1) +
geom_point(size = 5, col = "black", shape = 21) +
geom_label() +
facet_wrap(~mouse_ID) +

xlab(paste("PC1: ", pc1, "%", sep="")) +
ylab(paste("PC2: ", pc2, "%", sep="")) +
guides(fill = guide_legend(override.aes = list(shape = 22))) +
theme_bw()

dis_ait = dist(t(species.exp[,metadata$FVT == "Control"]), method = "euclidean")

#Perform a PERMANOVA (PERmutational Multivariate ANalysis Of VAriance) test.
vegan::adonis2(dis_ait ~ plate + Stress * Timepoint, data = metadata[metadata$FVT == "Control",],
method = "euclidean", permutations = 10000)

res = fw_glmmer(x = species.exp,
  f = ~ plate + Contrasts * Timepoint + (1|Proposed_mouse_ID),
  metadata = metadata, format = "wide", order = "ac", adjust.method = "Storey")
rescon_stress = fw_glmmer(x = species.exp[,metadata$FVT == "Control"],
  f = ~ plate + Stress * Timepoint + (1|Proposed_mouse_ID),
  metadata = metadata[metadata$FVT == "Control",], format = "wide", order = "ac",
adjust.method = "Storey")
resFVT_stress = fw_glmmer(x = species.exp[,metadata$Stress == "Stress"],
  f = ~ plate + FVT * Timepoint + (1|Proposed_mouse_ID),
  metadata = metadata[metadata$Stress == "Stress",], format = "wide", order = "ac",
adjust.method = "Storey")

res = cbind(res, con_vs_stress_p = rescon_stress$`anovas.Stress:Timepoint Pr(>F)` , FVT_vs_stress_p =
resFVT_stress$`anovas.FVT:Timepoint Pr(>F)` )

```

```
hist(res$`anovas.Contrasts:Timepoint Pr(>F).Storey`, xlim = c(0, 1), breaks = 20)
hist(res$`coefs.StressStress:TimepointPre Pr(>|t).BH`, xlim = c(0, 1), breaks = 20)
```

```
sum(res$`anovas.Stress:Timepoint Pr(>F).BH` < 0.1)
```

```
res[(res$`anovas.Stress:Timepoint Pr(>F).Storey` < 0.2),]$feature
res[(res$`coefs.StressStress:TimepointB Pr(>|t).Storey` < 0.2),]$feature
```

```
res <- res %>%
  mutate(Restored = case_when(
    `coefs.ContrastsStress_contrast:TimepointPre Pr(>|t).Storey` < 0.2 &
    `coefs.ContrastsStress_contrast:TimepointPre Pr(>|t)` < 0.05 &
    con_vs_stress_p < 0.1 &
    FVT_vs_stress_p < 0.1 ~ "Restored",
    T ~ " "))
```

```
res %>%
```

```
ggplot(aes(x = `coefs.ContrastsStress_contrast:TimepointPre Estimate`,
  y = `coefs.ContrastsStress_contrast:TimepointPre Pr(>|t)`),
  size = Restored,
  alpha = Restored,
  colour = Restored,
  fill = Restored,
  label = feature)) +
  geom_point(shape = 21) +
  ggrepel::geom_label_repel(data = subset(res, Restored == "Restored"), fill = "white", colour = "black")
+
```

```
geom_hline(yintercept = 0.05, linetype = "dashed", colour = "red") +
```

```
scale_y_continuous(trans=reverselog_trans(10)) +
```

```
scale_x_continuous(limits = c(-0.8, 0.8)) +
```

```
scale_size_manual(values = c("Restored" = 3, " " = 1.5)) +
```

```
scale_alpha_manual( values = c("Restored" = 1, " " = 0.7)) +
```

```
scale_colour_manual(values = c("Restored" = "black", " " = "gray")) +
```

```
scale_fill_manual( values = c("Restored" = "#2171b5", " " = "gray")) +
```

```
guides(fill = 'none', label = 'none', size = 'none', colour = 'none', alpha = 'none') +
```

```
ggtitle("Bacterial species affected by stress and restored by FVT") +
```

```
xlab(paste0("Effect size (", "\u03B2", ")")) +
```

```
ylab(paste0("p-value (log10-scaled)")) +
```

```
theme_bw()
```

```
t(species.exp) %>%
```

```
  cbind(metadata) %>%
```

```
  pivot_longer(!colnames(metadata)) %>%
```

```
  #mutate(value = log(value)) %>%
```

```
  #filter(FVT == "Control") %>%
```

```
  filter(name %in% res[(res$`anovas.Contrasts:Timepoint Pr(>F).Storey` < 0.2),]$feature) %>%
```

```
  #
```

```
  mutate(Timepoint = factor(Timepoint, levels = c("Pre", "Post"))) %>%
```

```
  mutate(Treatment = paste(FVT, Stress)) %>%
```

```
  # mutate(name = str_replace(name, ".*ales_", "")) %>%
```

```
  # mutate(Cluster = factor(Cluster, levels = c("NS", "Resilient", "Pain", "P.Coping", "Comorbid"))) %>%
```

```

# mutate(name = str_replace(name, "\\(", "\\n\\(")) %>%
#mutate(name = str_to_sentence(name)) %>%

ggplot(aes(x = interaction(Timepoint, Treatment), y = value)) +
geom_boxplot(aes(fill = Treatment), alpha = 1/2, coef = 100, position = position_dodge(1)) +
geom_line(aes(group = Proposed_mouse_ID), alpha = 1/4, linetype = "dashed") +
#geom_dotplot(binaxis = "y", stackdir = "center", position = position_dodge(2)) +
geom_point(aes(fill = Treatment), shape = 21, position = position_dodge(1)) +

facet_wrap(~name, scales = "free", ncol = 4) +
scale_fill_manual(values = c("Control Control" = "#8DA0CB",
                             "Control Stress" = "#FF7F00",
                             "FVT Stress" = "#1B9E77"), labels = c("Ctr", "Ctr Stress", "FVT Stress")) +
scale_x_discrete(labels = rep(c("Pre", "Post"), 3))+
xlab("") +
ylab("Species abundance (CLR)") +
theme_bw() +
ggtitle("Microbial Species Affected by Stress and Restored by Faecal Virome Transplantation") +
theme(text = element_text(size = 12), legend.background = element_rect(colour = "black"))

metadata = metadata[order(metadata$Proposed_mouse_ID),]

delta_sp = (species.exp[,metadata$Timepoint == "Post"]/log(2)) - (species.exp[,metadata$Timepoint ==
"Pre"]/log(2))

t(delta_sp) %>%
#t() %>%
#data.frame() %>%
cbind(metadata[metadata$Timepoint == "Pre",]) %>%
pivot_longer(!colnames(metadata)) %>%

```

```

mutate(Legend = paste(FVT, Stress)) %>%
filter(name %in% res[(res$` anovas.Contrasts:Timepoint Pr(>F).Storey` < 0.2),]$feature) %>%
group_by(name, Legend) %>%
summarise(Mean = round(mean(value), digits = 2)) %>%
ungroup() %>%
ggplot() +

aes(x = Legend, y = name, fill = Mean, label = Mean) +
geom_tile() +
geom_text(colour = "black") +
#facet_wrap(~Legend, scales = "free") +
scale_fill_gradientn(colors = c("#2166ac", "#2166ac", "#2166ac",
                                "#67a9cf", "#67a9cf",
                                "white", "white",
                                "#ef8a62", "#ef8a62",
                                "#b2182b", "#b2182b", "#b2182b"),
                    limits = c(-0.8, 0.8)) +
scale_y_discrete(position = "right", limits=rev) +
scale_x_discrete(labels = c("\U0394 Ctr", "\U0394 Ctr\nStress", "\U0394 FVT\nStress")) +
theme_bw() + xlab("") + ylab("") +
theme(text = element_text(size = 16))

```

Sankey plot linking virome to bacteriome

```

library(tidyverse)
library(Tjazi)
library(ggsankey)

ph_dic <-
read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/phage/Chris_stuff/whole_metagenome/filtered_master_taxa_
table.tsv", sep = "\t")

```

```
bac_list <-  
read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/phage_bac_integration/bacteriome.virome.matching.fvt.stress.0  
51022.csv", sep = ",")
```

```
POI <- tolower(bac_list[bac_list$Location == "Differential abundance spp.", 3])
```

```
POI = POI %>%
```

```
  str_replace(pattern = "actinobacteriota \\(actinobacteria\\)", replacement = "actinobacteriota") %>%
```

```
  str_replace(pattern = "bacillota \\(firmicutes\\)", replacement = "firmicutes") %>%
```

```
  str_replace(pattern = "firmicutes", replacement = "bacillota") %>%
```

```
  str_replace(pattern = "pseudomonadota \\(proteobacteria\\)", replacement = "proteobacteria") %>%
```

```
  str_replace(pattern = "proteobacteria", replacement = "pseudomonadota") %>%
```

```
  str_replace(pattern = "cyanobacteria/melainabacteria group", replacement = "cyanobacteria") %>%
```

```
  str_replace(pattern = "cyanobacteria/melainabacteria group", replacement = "cyanobacteria") %>%  
  str_to_title()
```

```
ph_hosts = ph_dic %>%
```

```
  filter(host_phylum != "p__Undetermined") %>%
```

```
  mutate(host_phylum = str_remove(host_phylum, "p__")) %>%
```

```
  mutate(host_phylum = str_remove(host_phylum, "_A")) %>%
```

```
  mutate(host_phylum = str_replace(host_phylum, pattern = "Firmicutes", replacement = "Bacillota"))  
  %>%
```

```
  mutate(host_phylum = str_replace(host_phylum, pattern = "Proteobacteria", replacement =  
  "Pseudomonadota")) %>%
```

```
  filter(host_phylum %in% unique(POI)) %>%
```

```
  dplyr::select(c(host_phylum, Family, Genus)) %>%
```

```
  filter(Family != "Parvoviridae") %>%
```

```

filter(Family != "Circoviridae") %>%
mutate(Family = dplyr::recode(Family, "Siphoviridae" = "Caudoviricetes", "Podoviridae" =
"Caudoviricetes", "Myoviridae" = "Caudoviricetes")) %>%
mutate(Family = dplyr::recode(Family, "Microviridae" = "Malgrandaviricetes")) %>%
mutate(Family = str_replace(Family, pattern = "Unassigned", replacement = "Unassigned class")) %>%
mutate(Genus = str_replace(Genus, pattern = "Unassigned", replacement = "Unassigned genus")) %>%

```

```
data.frame
```

```
colnames(ph_hosts) <- c("Bacterial Host Phylum", "Viral Class", "Viral Genus")
```

```
df1 = ph_hosts %>%
  make_long("Bacterial Host Phylum", "Viral Class", "Viral Genus")
```

```
dagg <- df1 %>%
  dplyr::group_by(node)%>%
  tally()
```

```
merge(df1, dagg, by.x = 'node', by.y = 'node', all.x = TRUE) %>%
```

```
ggplot() +
aes(x = x, next_x = next_x,
  node = node, next_node = next_node,
  fill = factor(node), label = paste0(node, ", n = ", n)) +
geom_sankey(flow.alpha = 0.5,
  node.color = "black",
  show.legend = FALSE) +
geom_sankey_label(size = 3, color = "black", fill= "white", hjust = -1/2) +
theme_bw() +
```

```
xlab("") + theme(axis.title = element_blank(), axis.text.y = element_blank(), axis.ticks =  
element_blank(), panel.grid = element_blank()) +  
scale_x_discrete(expand = c(.05, 1))
```

Targeted RNAseq GO enrichment

```
library(tidyverse)
```

```
library(patchwork)
```

```
amy = read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/GO_enrichment/genes_amy.csv", sep = ",", header = F)
```

```
hip = read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/GO_enrichment/genes_hip.csv", sep = ",", header = F)
```

```
s1 = read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/GO_enrichment/GO_terms/fear_response.csv", sep = ",",
```

```
s2 = read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/GO_enrichment/GO_terms/immune_system_process.csv",  
sep = ",",)
```

```
s3 =  
read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/GO_enrichment/GO_terms/regulation_of_neurotransmitter_levels.csv", sep = ",",)
```

```
s4 =  
read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/GO_enrichment/GO_terms/regulation_of_postsynaptic_membrane_neurotransmitter_receptor_levels.csv", sep = ",",)
```

```
s5 =  
read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/GO_enrichment/GO_terms/regulation_of_viral_process.csv",  
sep = ",",)
```

```
s6 = read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/GO_enrichment/GO_terms/response_to_stress.csv", sep =  
",")
```

```
s7 = read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/GO_enrichment/GO_terms/social_behavior.csv", sep =  
",")
```

```
s8 = read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/GO_enrichment/GO_terms/viral_process.csv", sep = ",",)
```

```
amy_rest = read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/amygdala_restored_genes.csv", sep = ",",)
```

```
hip_rest = read.delim("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/hippocampus_restored_genes.csv", sep = ",",)
```

```
#dim(genes_hip)
10248
#dim(genes_amy)
20903

#
# phyper(q, m, n, k, lower.tail = TRUE, log.p = FALSE)
#
# x, q vector of quantiles representing the number of white balls drawn
# without replacement from an urn which contains both black and white
# balls.
#
# m the number of white balls in the urn.
#
# n the number of black balls in the urn.
#
# k the number of balls drawn from the urn.
# So using your data:
#
# phyper(62,1998,5260-1998,131)
# [1] 0.989247

res_amy = data.frame(Term = c("fear_response",
                              "immune_system_process",
                              "regulation_of_neurotransmitter_levels",
                              "regulation_of_postsynaptic_membrane_neurotransmitter_receptor_levels",
                              "regulation_of_viral_process",
                              "response_to_stress",
                              "social_behavior",
                              "viral_process"),
```

p = NA, hits = NA, genes = NA, exp = NA)

#s1

res_amy[1, 2] =

```
phyper(q = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s1$Symbol)), toupper(amy_rest$gene_ID))),
      m = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s1$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3))),
      n = (nrow(amy) - length(intersect(unique(toupper(s1$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))),
      k = nrow(amy_rest), lower.tail = F)
```

res_amy[1, 3] =

```
length(intersect(unique(toupper(s1$Symbol)), toupper(amy_rest$gene_ID)))
```

res_amy[1, 4] =

```
length(intersect(unique(toupper(s1$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))
```

res_amy[1,5] =

```
(length(intersect(unique(toupper(s1$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3))) * nrow(amy_rest)) / nrow(amy)
```

#s2

res_amy[2, 2] =

```
phyper(q = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s2$Symbol)), toupper(amy_rest$gene_ID))),
      m = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s2$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3))),
      n = (nrow(amy) - length(intersect(unique(toupper(s2$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))),
      k = nrow(amy_rest), lower.tail = F)
```

res_amy[2, 3] =

```
length(intersect(unique(toupper(s2$Symbol)), toupper(amy_rest$gene_ID)))
```

res_amy[2, 4] =

```
length(intersect(unique(toupper(s2$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))
```

res_amy[2,5] =

```
(length(intersect(unique(toupper(s2$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3))) * nrow(amy_rest)) / nrow(amy)
```

#s3

res_amy[3, 2] =

```

phyper(q = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s3$Symbol)), toupper(amy_rest$gene_ID))),
      m = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s3$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3))),
      n = (nrow(amy) - length(intersect(unique(toupper(s3$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))),
      k = nrow(amy_rest),lower.tail = F)
res_amy[3, 3] =
  length(intersect(unique(toupper(s3$Symbol)), toupper(amy_rest$gene_ID)))
res_amy[3, 4] =
  length(intersect(unique(toupper(s3$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))
res_amy[3,5] =
  (length(intersect(unique(toupper(s3$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))*nrow(amy_rest))/nrow(amy)

```

```
#s4
```

```

res_amy[4, 2] =
  phyper(q = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s4$Symbol)), toupper(amy_rest$gene_ID))),
        m = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s4$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3))),
        n = (nrow(amy) - length(intersect(unique(toupper(s4$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))),
        k = nrow(amy_rest),lower.tail = F)
res_amy[4, 3] =
  length(intersect(unique(toupper(s4$Symbol)), toupper(amy_rest$gene_ID)))
res_amy[4, 4] =
  length(intersect(unique(toupper(s4$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))
res_amy[4,5] =
  (length(intersect(unique(toupper(s4$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))*nrow(amy_rest))/nrow(amy)

```

```
#s5
```

```

res_amy[5, 2] =
  phyper(q = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s5$Symbol)), toupper(amy_rest$gene_ID))),
        m = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s5$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3))),
        n = (nrow(amy) - length(intersect(unique(toupper(s5$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))),
        k = nrow(amy_rest),lower.tail = F)
res_amy[5, 3] =

```

```
length(intersect(unique(toupper(s5$Symbol)), toupper(amy_rest$gene_ID)))
res_amy[5, 4] =
length(intersect(unique(toupper(s5$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))
res_amy[5,5] =
(length(intersect(unique(toupper(s5$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))*nrow(amy_rest))/nrow(amy)
```

```
#s6
```

```
res_amy[6, 2] =
phyper(q = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s6$Symbol)), toupper(amy_rest$gene_ID))),
      m = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s6$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3))),
      n = (nrow(amy) - length(intersect(unique(toupper(s6$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))),
      k = nrow(amy_rest),lower.tail = F)
res_amy[6, 3] =
length(intersect(unique(toupper(s6$Symbol)), toupper(amy_rest$gene_ID)))
res_amy[6, 4] =
length(intersect(unique(toupper(s6$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))
res_amy[6,5] =
(length(intersect(unique(toupper(s6$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))*nrow(amy_rest))/nrow(amy)
```

```
#s7
```

```
res_amy[7, 2] =
phyper(q = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s7$Symbol)), toupper(amy_rest$gene_ID))),
      m = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s7$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3))),
      n = (nrow(amy) - length(intersect(unique(toupper(s7$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))),
      k = nrow(amy_rest),lower.tail = F)
res_amy[7, 3] =
length(intersect(unique(toupper(s7$Symbol)), toupper(amy_rest$gene_ID)))
res_amy[7, 4] =
length(intersect(unique(toupper(s7$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))
res_amy[7,5] =
(length(intersect(unique(toupper(s7$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))*nrow(amy_rest))/nrow(amy)
```

```

#s8
res_amy[8, 2] =
  phyper(q = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s8$Symbol)), toupper(amy_rest$gene_ID))),
        m = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s8$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3))),
        n = (nrow(amy) - length(intersect(unique(toupper(s8$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))),
        k = nrow(amy_rest), lower.tail = F)
res_amy[8, 3] =
  length(intersect(unique(toupper(s8$Symbol)), toupper(amy_rest$gene_ID)))
res_amy[8, 4] =
  length(intersect(unique(toupper(s8$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))
res_amy[8,5] =
  (length(intersect(unique(toupper(s8$Symbol)), toupper(amy$V3)))*nrow(amy_rest))/nrow(amy)

res_amy$ratio = res_amy$hits / res_amy$genes
res_amy$fold = res_amy$hits / res_amy$exp
res_amy$logfold = log2(res_amy$fold)

p_amy <- ggplot(res_amy) +
  aes(xend = 0, yend = Term, x = logfold, y = Term, fill = p < 0.05) +
  geom_segment(size = 1.5) +
  geom_point(shape = 21, size = 3) +
  #scale_x_continuous(limits = c(0, 1)) +
  scale_fill_manual(values = c("TRUE" = "#d73027", "FALSE" = "white")) +
  scale_y_discrete(position = "right") +
  ylab("") + xlab("log2-fold enrichment") +
  theme_bw() + ggtitle("Targeted Functional Enrichment in Amygdalar Restored Genes")

#Hippocampus -----

```

```

#
# phyper(q, m, n, k, lower.tail = TRUE, log.p = FALSE)
#
# x, q vector of quantiles representing the number of white balls drawn
# without replacement from an urn which contains both black and white
# balls.
#
# m the number of white balls in the urn.
#
# n the number of black balls in the urn.
#
# k the number of balls drawn from the urn.
# So using your data:
#
# phyper(62,1998,5260-1998,131)
# [1] 0.989247

res_hip = data.frame(Term = c("fear_response",
                             "immune_system_process",
                             "regulation_of_neurotransmitter_levels",
                             "regulation_of_postsynaptic_membrane_neurotransmitter_receptor_levels",
                             "regulation_of_viral_process",
                             "response_to_stress",
                             "social_behavior",
                             "viral_process"),
                    p = NA, hits = NA, genes = NA, exp = NA)

#s1
res_hip[1, 2] =

```

```

phyper(q = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s1$Symbol)), toupper(hip_rest$gene_ID))),
      m = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s1$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3))),
      n = (nrow(hip) - length(intersect(unique(toupper(s1$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))),
      k = nrow(hip_rest),lower.tail = F)
res_hip[1,3] =
  length(intersect(unique(toupper(s1$Symbol)), toupper(hip_rest$gene_ID)))
res_hip[1,4] =
  length(intersect(unique(toupper(s1$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))
res_hip[1,5] =
  (length(intersect(unique(toupper(s1$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))*nrow(hip_rest))/nrow(hip)

```

#s2

```

res_hip[2, 2] =
  phyper(q = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s2$Symbol)), toupper(hip_rest$gene_ID))),
        m = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s2$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3))),
        n = (nrow(hip) - length(intersect(unique(toupper(s2$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))),
        k = nrow(hip_rest),lower.tail = F)
res_hip[2, 3] =
  length(intersect(unique(toupper(s2$Symbol)), toupper(hip_rest$gene_ID)))
res_hip[2, 4] =
  length(intersect(unique(toupper(s2$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))
res_hip[2,5] =
  (length(intersect(unique(toupper(s2$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))*nrow(hip_rest))/nrow(hip)

```

#s3

```

res_hip[3, 2] =
  phyper(q = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s3$Symbol)), toupper(hip_rest$gene_ID))),
        m = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s3$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3))),
        n = (nrow(hip) - length(intersect(unique(toupper(s3$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))),
        k = nrow(hip_rest),lower.tail = F)
res_hip[3, 3] =

```

```

length(intersect(unique(toupper(s3$Symbol)), toupper(hip_rest$gene_ID)))
res_hip[3, 4] =
length(intersect(unique(toupper(s3$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))
res_hip[3,5] =
(length(intersect(unique(toupper(s3$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))*nrow(hip_rest))/nrow(hip)

#s4
res_hip[4, 2] =
phyper(q = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s4$Symbol)), toupper(hip_rest$gene_ID))),
      m = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s4$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3))),
      n = (nrow(hip) - length(intersect(unique(toupper(s4$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))),
      k = nrow(hip_rest),lower.tail = F)
res_hip[4, 3] =
length(intersect(unique(toupper(s4$Symbol)), toupper(hip_rest$gene_ID)))
res_hip[4, 4] =
length(intersect(unique(toupper(s4$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))
res_hip[4,5] =
(length(intersect(unique(toupper(s4$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))*nrow(hip_rest))/nrow(hip)

#s5
res_hip[5, 2] =
phyper(q = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s5$Symbol)), toupper(hip_rest$gene_ID))),
      m = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s5$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3))),
      n = (nrow(hip) - length(intersect(unique(toupper(s5$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))),
      k = nrow(hip_rest),lower.tail = F)
res_hip[5, 3] =
length(intersect(unique(toupper(s5$Symbol)), toupper(hip_rest$gene_ID)))
res_hip[5, 4] =
length(intersect(unique(toupper(s5$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))
res_hip[5,5] =
(length(intersect(unique(toupper(s5$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))*nrow(hip_rest))/nrow(hip)

```

```
#s6
```

```
res_hip[6, 2] =
```

```
  phyper(q = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s6$Symbol)), toupper(hip_rest$gene_ID))),  
        m = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s6$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3))),  
        n = (nrow(hip) - length(intersect(unique(toupper(s6$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))),  
        k = nrow(hip_rest), lower.tail = F)
```

```
res_hip[6, 3] =
```

```
  length(intersect(unique(toupper(s6$Symbol)), toupper(hip_rest$gene_ID)))
```

```
res_hip[6, 4] =
```

```
  length(intersect(unique(toupper(s6$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))
```

```
res_hip[6,5] =
```

```
  (length(intersect(unique(toupper(s6$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))*nrow(hip_rest))/nrow(hip)
```

```
#s7
```

```
res_hip[7, 2] =
```

```
  phyper(q = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s7$Symbol)), toupper(hip_rest$gene_ID))),  
        m = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s7$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3))),  
        n = (nrow(hip) - length(intersect(unique(toupper(s7$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3))),  
        k = nrow(hip_rest), lower.tail = F)
```

```
res_hip[7, 3] =
```

```
  length(intersect(unique(toupper(s7$Symbol)), toupper(hip_rest$gene_ID)))
```

```
res_hip[7, 4] =
```

```
  length(intersect(unique(toupper(s7$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))
```

```
res_hip[7,5] =
```

```
  (length(intersect(unique(toupper(s7$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))*nrow(hip_rest))/nrow(hip)
```

```
#s8
```

```
res_hip[8, 2] =
```

```
  phyper(q = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s8$Symbol)), toupper(hip_rest$gene_ID))),  
        m = length(intersect(unique(toupper(s8$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3))),
```

```

n = (nrow(hip) - length(intersect(unique(toupper(s8$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3))))),
k = nrow(hip_rest), lower.tail = F)
res_hip[8, 3] =
  length(intersect(unique(toupper(s8$Symbol)), toupper(hip_rest$gene_ID)))
res_hip[8, 4] =
  length(intersect(unique(toupper(s8$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))
res_hip[8,5] =
  (length(intersect(unique(toupper(s8$Symbol)), toupper(hip$V3)))*nrow(hip_rest))/nrow(hip)

res_hip$ratio = res_hip$hits / res_hip$genes
res_hip$fold = res_hip$hits / res_hip$exp
res_hip$logfold = log2(res_hip$fold)

rbind(res_amy, res_hip) %>%
  mutate(Region = c(rep("amygdala",8), rep("hippocampus", 8))) %>%
  mutate(new_term = rep(c("Fear response", "Immune system process", "Neurotransmitter level
modulation",
  "Postsynaptic neurotransmitter receptor effector",
  NA, "Stress response", "Social behavior",
  "Viral process"), 2)) %>%
  filter(!is.na(new_term)) %>%
  ggplot() +
  aes(y = logfold, x = new_term, fill = p < 0.05, colour = Region, group = Region) +
  geom_linerange(size = 1.75, aes(xmin = new_term, xmax = new_term, ymin = 0, ymax = logfold),
position = position_dodge(0.5), colour = "black") +
  geom_linerange(size = 1.5, aes(xmin = new_term, xmax = new_term, ymin = 0, ymax = logfold),
position = position_dodge(0.5)) +
  geom_point(shape = 21, size = 3, position = position_dodge(0.5), colour = "black") +
  #geom_text(aes(label = "🔔"), position = position_dodge(0.5)) +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 0, linetype = "dashed", colour = "red", alpha = 2/3) +
  scale_fill_manual(values = c("TRUE" = "#8AB2BE", "FALSE" = "white")) +

```

```

scale_x_discrete(position = "top", limits = rev(c("Fear response",
        "Immune system process",
        "Neurotransmitter level modulation",
        "Postsynaptic neurotransmitter receptor effector",
        "Stress response",
        "Social behavior",
        "Viral process")))) +
scale_colour_manual(values = c("amygdala" = "#40f297ff", "hippocampus" = "#d472e5ff")) +
ylab("log2-fold enrichment") + xlab("") +
theme_bw() +
ggtitle("Targeted Functional Enrichment in Restored Genes by Brain Region") +
coord_flip()

```

RNAseq volcano plots & restoration contrasts

```
library(broom)
```

```
library(tidyverse)
```

```
library(Tjazi)
```

```
library(patchwork)
```

```
#load custom function for y-axis
```

```
reverselog_trans <- function(base = exp(1)) {
```

```
  trans <- function(x) -log(x, base)
```

```
  inv <- function(x) base^(-x)
```

```
  scales::trans_new(paste0("reverselog-", format(base)), trans, inv,
```

```
    scales::log_breaks(base = base),
```

```
    domain = c(1e-100, Inf))
```

```
}
```

```
setwd("~/Documents/PhD/Nate/FVT/")
```

```
#Load and prepare RNAseq counts data
```

```
counts = read.delim("RNASEQ/gene_counts.txt", sep = "\t", row.names = 2)[-1]
```

```
metadata = read.delim("metadata_KO_FVT.csv", sep = ",")
```

```
metadata = metadata[metadata$Timepoint == "After",]
```

```
metadata_amy = metadata[metadata$ID != "hkFVTStress36A_Abundance",]
```

```
counts_amy = counts[,metadata_amy$RNAseq_ID_Amygdala]
```

```
metadata_amy$Full_treatment <- factor(metadata_amy$Full_treatment)
```

```
metadata_hip = metadata[!metadata$ID %in% c("hkFVTStress17A_Abundance",  
"hkFVTStress36A_Abundance"),]
```

```
counts_hip = counts[,metadata_hip$RNAseq_ID_Hippocampus]
```

```
metadata_hip$Full_treatment <- factor(metadata_hip$Full_treatment)
```

```
genes_amy <- counts_amy
```

```
genes_amy <- apply(genes_amy,c(1,2),function(x) as.numeric(as.character(x)))
```

```
genes_amy <- genes_amy[apply(genes_amy == 0, 1, sum) <= round(ncol(genes_amy) * 0.5), ]  
#remove rows with 5% or fewer hits
```

```
genes_amy.exp = clr_lite(genes_amy, method = "const", replicates = 1)
```

```
genes_hip <- counts_hip
```

```
genes_hip <- apply(genes_hip,c(1,2),function(x) as.numeric(as.character(x)))
```

```
genes_hip <- genes_hip[apply(genes_hip == 0, 1, sum) <= round(ncol(genes_hip) * 0.5), ] #remove  
rows with 5% or fewer hits
```

```
genes_hip <- genefilter::varFilter(genes_hip, var.cutoff = 0.5)
```

```
genes_hip.exp = clr_lite(genes_hip, method = "const", replicates = 1)
```

```
#Amygdala
```

```
mat_restored = cbind(c(1/2, -1, 1/2, 0))  
rownames(mat_restored) <- levels(metadata_amy$Full_treatment)  
colnames(mat_restored) <- c("Restored")
```

```
res_amy_restored = genes_amy.exp %>%  
  t() %>%  
  data.frame() %>%  
  add_column(Treatment = metadata_amy$Full_treatment) %>%  
  pivot_longer(!Treatment) %>%  
  #filter(name %in% c("ENSMUSG00000000001")) %>%  
  group_by(name) %>%  
  summarize(lm(value ~ Treatment,  
              contrasts = list(Treatment = mat_restored),  
              data = cur_data() ) %>% tidy() ) %>%  
  ungroup() %>%  
  filter(term != "(Intercept)")
```

```
res_amy_ConvStress = genes_amy.exp %>%  
  t() %>%  
  data.frame() %>%  
  add_column(Treatment = metadata_amy$Full_treatment) %>%  
  pivot_longer(!Treatment) %>%  
  filter(Treatment %in% c("Ctr", "CtrStress")) %>%  
  group_by(name) %>%  
  summarize(lm(value ~ Treatment,  
              data = cur_data() ) %>% tidy() ) %>%
```

```

ungroup() %>%
filter(term != "(Intercept)") %>%
mutate(term = str_replace(term, "Treatment1", "TreatmentCtrStress"))

res_amy_FVTvStress = genes_amy.exp %>%
t() %>%
data.frame() %>%
add_column(Treatment = metadata_amy$Full_treatment) %>%
pivot_longer(!Treatment) %>%
filter(Treatment %in% c("FVTStress", "CtrStress")) %>%
group_by(name) %>%
summarize(lm(value ~ Treatment,
             data = cur_data() ) %>% tidy()) %>%
ungroup() %>%
filter(term != "(Intercept)") %>%
mutate(term = str_replace(term, "Treatment1", "TreatmentFVTStress"))

res_amy_ConvStress$p.value %>% hist
res_amy_restored$p.value %>% hist
hist(df$q.value_TreatmentRestored)

rbind(res_amy_restored, res_amy_ConvStress) %>%
rbind(res_amy_FVTvStress) %>%
pivot_wider(names_from = term, values_from = c(estimate, std.error, statistic, p.value)) %>%
mutate(q.value_TreatmentRestored = p.adjust(p.value_TreatmentRestored, method = "BH")) %>%
filter(q.value_TreatmentRestored < 0.2 &
       p.value_TreatmentRestored < 0.05 &
       p.value_TreatmentCtrStress < 0.1 &
       p.value_TreatmentFVTStress < 0.1 &
       abs(estimate_TreatmentRestored) < 3) %>%
.$name -> GOI

```

```
length(GOI)
```

```
#GOI %>% write.csv(file = "amygdala_restored_genes.csv", row.names = F)
```

```
#https://www.biotoools.fr/mouse/ensembl_symbol_converter
```

```
hist(df$estimate_TreatmentRestored)
```

```
genes_amy.exp %>%
```

```
t() %>%
```

```
data.frame() %>%
```

```
add_column(Treatment = metadata_amy$Full_treatment) %>%
```

```
pivot_longer(!Treatment) %>%
```

```
filter(name %in% sample(GOI, 48)) %>%
```

```
ggplot(aes(x = Treatment, y = value, fill = Treatment)) +
```

```
geom_boxplot(alpha = 1/2) +
```

```
geom_point(shape = 21) +
```

```
theme_bw() +
```

```
scale_fill_manual(values = c("Ctr" = "white",
```

```
  "CtrStress" = "#a00000",
```

```
  "FVTStress" = "#d4d4d4",
```

```
  "hkFVTStress" = "#606060")) +
```

```
facet_wrap(~name, scales = "free_y", ncol = 6)
```

```

hist(df$q.value_TreatmentRestored)

volc_amy <- rbind(res_amy_restored, res_amy_ConvStress) %>%
  rbind(res_amy_FVTvStress) %>%
  pivot_wider(names_from = term, values_from = c(estimate, std.error, statistic, p.value)) %>%
  mutate(q.value_TreatmentRestored = p.adjust(p.value_TreatmentRestored, method = "BH")) %>%

  mutate(Restored = case_when(
    q.value_TreatmentRestored < 0.2 &
      p.value_TreatmentRestored < 0.05 &
      p.value_TreatmentCtrStress < 0.1 &
      p.value_TreatmentFVTStress < 0.1 ~ "Restored",
    T ~ " ")) %>%
  filter(abs(estimate_TreatmentRestored) < 3) %>%
  ggplot(aes(x = estimate_TreatmentRestored,
    y = p.value_TreatmentRestored,
    alpha = Restored,
    colour = Restored,
    fill = Restored)) +
  geom_point(shape = 21) +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 0.05, linetype = "dashed", colour = "red") +
  scale_y_continuous(trans=reverselog_trans(10)) +
  scale_x_continuous(limits = c(-0.8, 0.8)) +
  scale_alpha_manual(values = c("Restored" = 1,
    " " = 0.1)) +
  scale_colour_manual(values = c("Restored" = "black",
    " " = "gray")) +
  scale_fill_manual(values = c("Restored" = "#2171b5",
    " " = "gray")) +
  xlab(paste0("Effect size (", "\u03B2", ")")) +
  ylab(paste0("p-value (log10-scaled)")) +

```

```
guides(alpha = 'none', colour = 'none', fill = 'none') +  
ggtitle("Genes affected by stress and restored by FVT in the amygdala") +  
theme_bw()
```

```
volc_amy
```

```
#Hippocampus
```

```
mat_restored = cbind(c(1/2, -1, 1/2, 0))
```

```
rownames(mat_restored) <- levels(metadata_hip$Full_treatment)
```

```
colnames(mat_restored) <- c("Restored")
```

```
res_hip_restored = genes_hip.exp %>%  
  t() %>%  
  data.frame() %>%  
  add_column(Treatment = metadata_hip$Full_treatment) %>%  
  pivot_longer(!Treatment) %>%  
  #filter(name %in% c("ENSMUSG00000000001")) %>%  
  group_by(name) %>%  
  summarize(lm(value ~ Treatment,  
               contrasts = list(Treatment = mat_restored),  
               data = cur_data() ) %>% tidy() %>%  
  ungroup() %>%  
  filter(term != "(Intercept)")
```

```
hist(res_hip_restored$p.value)
```

```
res_hip_ConvStress = genes_hip.exp %>%  
  t() %>%  
  data.frame() %>%  
  add_column(Treatment = metadata_hip$Full_treatment) %>%  
  pivot_longer(!Treatment) %>%  
  filter(Treatment %in% c("Ctr", "CtrStress")) %>%  
  group_by(name) %>%  
  summarize(lm(value ~ Treatment,  
               data = cur_data() ) %>% tidy()) %>%  
  ungroup() %>%  
  filter(term != "(Intercept)") %>%  
  mutate(term = str_replace(term, "Treatment1", "TreatmentCtrStress"))
```

```
res_hip_FVTvStress = genes_hip.exp %>%  
  t() %>%  
  data.frame() %>%  
  add_column(Treatment = metadata_hip$Full_treatment) %>%  
  pivot_longer(!Treatment) %>%  
  filter(Treatment %in% c("FVTStress", "CtrStress")) %>%  
  group_by(name) %>%  
  summarize(lm(value ~ Treatment,  
               data = cur_data() ) %>% tidy()) %>%  
  ungroup() %>%  
  filter(term != "(Intercept)") %>%  
  mutate(term = str_replace(term, "Treatment1", "TreatmentFVTStress"))
```

```
res_hip_ConvStress$p.value %>% hist
```

```

rbind(res_hip_restored, res_hip_ConvStress) %>%
  rbind(res_hip_FVTvStress) %>%
  pivot_wider(names_from = term, values_from = c(estimate, std.error, statistic, p.value)) %>%
  mutate(q.value_TreatmentRestored = p.adjust(p.value_TreatmentRestored, method = "BH")) %>%
  filter(q.value_TreatmentRestored < 0.2 &
         p.value_TreatmentRestored < 0.05 &
         p.value_TreatmentCtrStress < 0.1 &
         p.value_TreatmentFVTStress < 0.1 &
         abs(estimate_TreatmentRestored) < 3) %>%
  .$name -> GOI

#GOI %>% write.csv(file = "hippocampus_restored_genes.csv", row.names = F)
#https://www.biotoools.fr/mouse/ensembl_symbol_converter

```

GOI

```
df[df$name == "ENSMUSG00000024222",] %>% view
```

```

genes_hip.exp %>%
  t() %>%
  data.frame() %>%
  add_column(Treatment = metadata_hip$Full_treatment) %>%
  pivot_longer(!Treatment) %>%
  filter(name %in% sample(GOI, 50)) %>%

```

```

ggplot(aes(x = Treatment, y = value)) +
geom_boxplot() +
geom_point() +
theme_bw() +
facet_wrap(~name, scales = "free_y")

```

```

volc_hip <- rbind(res_hip_restored, res_hip_ConvStress) %>%
  rbind(res_hip_FVTvStress) %>%
  pivot_wider(names_from = term, values_from = c(estimate, std.error, statistic, p.value)) %>%
  mutate(q.value_TreatmentRestored = p.adjust(p.value_TreatmentRestored, method = "BH")) %>%

```

```

mutate(Restored = case_when(
  q.value_TreatmentRestored < 0.2 &
  p.value_TreatmentRestored < 0.05 &
  p.value_TreatmentCtrStress < 0.1 &
  p.value_TreatmentFVTStress < 0.1 ~ "Restored",
  T ~ " ")) %>%

```

```

filter(abs(estimate_TreatmentRestored) < 3) %>%

```

```

ggplot(aes(x = estimate_TreatmentRestored,
  y = p.value_TreatmentRestored,
  alpha = Restored,
  colour = Restored,
  fill = Restored)) +
geom_point(shape = 21) +
geom_hline(yintercept = 0.05, linetype = "dashed", colour = "red") +
scale_y_continuous(trans=reverselog_trans(10)) +
scale_x_continuous(limits = c(-0.8, 0.8)) +
scale_alpha_manual(values = c("Restored" = 1,
  " " = 0.1)) +
scale_colour_manual(values = c("Restored" = "black",

```

```

    " "      = "gray")) +
scale_fill_manual(values = c("Restored" = "#2171b5",
    " "      = "gray")) +
xlab(paste0("Effect size (", "\u03B2", ")") +
ylab(paste0("p-value (log10-scaled)")) +

guides(alpha = 'none', colour = 'none', fill = 'none') +
ggtitle("Genes affected by stress and restored by FVT in the hippocampus") +
theme_bw()

volc_hip

#(pca_amy + ggtitle("PCA of amygdala") + pca_hip + ggtitle("PCA of hippocampus")) /
(volc_amy + volc_hip) + plot_layout(guides = 'collect')

```

Python scripts

Split_orfs_for_hmmer

```

from Bio import SeqIO
from sys import argv
from decimal import Decimal, ROUND_HALF_UP

```

```

# argv[1] = fasta file to split
# argv[2] = how many ways to split it
# argv[3] = prefix (including path)
# argv[4] = output file extension

```

```

records = []

```

```

argv[2] = int(argv[2])

```

```

for record in SeqIO.parse(argv[1], 'fasta'):
    records.append(record)

seq_bins = {}
for i in range(1, argv[2] + 1):
    if i == 1:
        seq_bins[i] = records[:int(Decimal(len(records)/argv[2]).quantize(0, ROUND_HALF_UP))]
    elif i == argv[2]:
        seq_bins[i] = records[int(Decimal(len(records)/argv[2]).quantize(0, ROUND_HALF_UP)*(i-1)):]
    else:
        seq_bins[i] = records[int(Decimal(len(records)/argv[2]).quantize(0, ROUND_HALF_UP)*(i-1)):int(Decimal(len(records)/argv[2]).quantize(0, ROUND_HALF_UP)*i)]

for i in range(1, argv[2] + 1):
    SeqIO.write(seq_bins[i], '{}_{} {}'.format(argv[3], i, argv[4]), 'fasta')

```

Remove_16S_hit_contigs

```

from sys import argv
import pandas as pd
from Bio import SeqIO

# argv[1] = path to barrnap output
# argv[2] = path to good_viral_contigs fasta
# argv[3] = path for output file

# import first column of barrnap output (containing the names of contigs that were hit)
df = pd.read_csv(argv[1], sep = '\t', usecols=[0], comment='#', names=['contig'])

# convert column to list of unique contig names
bad_contigs = list(df['contig'].unique())

# read through good_viral_contigs fasta and only keep contigs not in bad_contigs list

```

```

keep_contigs = []
for record in SeqIO.parse(argv[2], 'fasta'):
    if record.id not in bad_contigs:
        keep_contigs.append(record)

# write kept contigs to file
SeqIO.write(keep_contigs,argv[3],'fasta')

```

Replace_spike_contig

```

from ast import arg
import pandas as pd
from sys import argv
# import numpy as np
from Bio import SeqIO
# from collections import Counter

# input variable
# argv[1] = output of blasting spike vs contigs
# argv[2] = contig multifasta
# argv[3] = fasta file containing spike sequence
# argv[4] = output fasta path

def check_total_bases_covered(df):
    new_df = {'sseqid':[], 'slen':[], 'covered_base_length': []}
    for i in df['sseqid'].unique():
        ranges = 0
        ranges = set()
        for index, row in df[df['sseqid'] == i].iterrows():
            start = min([row['sstart'], row['send']])
            end = max([row['sstart'], row['send']])
            ranges.update(range(start - 1 , end))

```

```

    new_df['sseqid'].append(i)
    new_df['slen'].append(row['slen'])
    new_df['covered_base_length'].append(len(ranges)) # issue around here where simple table contains
some with value > 1
    new_df = pd.DataFrame.from_dict(new_df)
    return new_df

# load in blast database
df = pd.read_csv(argv[1], sep = '\t', names=['qseqid', 'sseqid', 'pident', 'length', 'mismatch', 'gapopen',
'qstart', 'qend', 'qlen', 'sstart', 'send', 'slen', 'evalue', 'bitscore'])

# store length of spike sequence
spike_length = df['qlen'].unique()[0]

# filter to remove hits with < 90% id
df = df[df['pident'] > 90]

# calculate how many bases for each contig covered by blast vs spike
df = check_total_bases_covered(df)

# filter to keep only contigs that are matched > 90% of their contigs length or where where the spike is
covered by >90 % (this latter filter will allow any chimeras to be caught)
df = df[(df['covered_base_length'] > df['slen'] * 0.9) | (df['covered_base_length'] > spike_length * 0.9)]

# identify contig covered the greatest amount by spike
spike_hit = df.sort_values(by='covered_base_length', ascending=False).iloc[0]['sseqid']

# load in contig fasta and collect NON-spike contigs
keep_contigs = []
for record in SeqIO.parse(argv[2], 'fasta'):
    if record.id != spike_hit:
        keep_contigs.append(record)

```

```
# append fasta sequence of the spike
for record in SeqIO.parse(argv[3], 'fasta'):
    keep_contigs.append(record)
```

```
# write all contigs to file
SeqIO.write(keep_contigs,argv[4],'fasta')
```

Parse_bacphlip_results

```
import pandas as pd
from sys import argv
```

```
# input variable
# argv[1] = cut off for each lifestyle type
# argv[2] = bacphlip input path
# argv[3] = output file path
```

```
# import bacphlip dataframe
df = pd.read_csv(argv[2], sep='\t')
```

```
# rename columns
df.columns = ['contig', 'virulent', 'temperate']
```

```
# create a result column that just says which ones are virulent vs temperate based on the argv[1] cutoff
df['result'] = df.apply(lambda x: 'virulent' if x['virulent'] >= float(argv[1]) and x['temperate'] <
float(argv[1]) else ('temperate' if x['temperate'] >= float(argv[1]) and x['virulent'] < float(argv[1]) else
'undetermined'), axis=1)
```

```
# write new table to file
df.to_csv(argv[3], sep='\t', index=False)
```

Get_master_viral_taxa_table

```

from sys import argv
from glob import glob
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np

# argv[1] = path to vcontact2 genome_by_genome_overview.csv for viral contig db
# argv[2] = path to DemoVir_assignments.txt for viral contig db
# argv[3] = path to parsed bacphlip output file (XXXX.bacphlip_filtered) for viral contig db
# argv[4] = path to Host_prediction_to_genus_m90.csv from iphop for viral contig db
# argv[5] = desired output path for master taxa doc

##### process vcontact2 df #####

# import vcontact2 dataframe
vcontact_df = pd.read_csv(argv[1])

# collect list of VCs that hit the phage in the contig db
hit_vcs = [x for x in vcontact_df['VC'][(vcontact_df['Genome'].str.split('~').str[-1].str.startswith('k141_') |
(vcontact_df['Genome'].str.startswith('ENA'))].unique() if str(x) != 'nan']

# make a dataframe containing only contigs from contig db
contig_df = vcontact_df[(vcontact_df['Genome'].str.split('~').str[-1].str.startswith('k141_') |
(vcontact_df['Genome'].str.startswith('ENA'))].reset_index(drop=True))
contig_df = contig_df[['Genome', 'VC Status', 'VC', 'VC Size']]

# create a dataframe containing relatives to the contigs db... i.e. those belonging to the hit VCs
relatives_df = vcontact_df[((vcontact_df['VC'].isin(hit_vcs)) & ((~vcontact_df['Genome'].str.split('~').str[-1].str.startswith('k141_') |
(vcontact_df['Genome'].str.startswith('ENA'))))].reset_index(drop=True))

# cycle through contig db VCs and extract most common taxa for each VC
VC_taxa_df = {'VC': [], 'Kingdom': [], 'Phylum': [], 'Class': [], 'Order': [], 'Family': [], 'Genus': []}
for i in hit_vcs:

```

```

sub_df = relatives_df[relatives_df['VC'] == i]
VC_taxa_df['VC'].append(i)
for j in ['Kingdom', 'Phylum', 'Class', 'Order', 'Family', 'Genus']:
    if len(sub_df) == 0:
        VC_taxa_df[j].append('Unassigned')
    else:
        taxa = sub_df.groupby(['VC'])[j].agg(lambda x: x.value_counts().index[0]).reset_index()
        taxa.columns = ['VC', 'taxa']
        VC_taxa_df[j].append(taxa['taxa'].iloc[0])
VC_taxa_df = pd.DataFrame.from_dict(VC_taxa_df)

# merge the VC taxa df with the contig df
contig_df = contig_df.merge(VC_taxa_df, on='VC', how='left')

# add column to say that these taxa were assigned via vcontact2
contig_df['taxa_tool'] = 'vcontact2'

#####

##### process demovir #####

def update_demovir_taxa(x_VC, x_Genome, x_Order, x_Family, x_Genus, x_taxa_tool, demovir_df):
    if ((x_Order == 'Unassigned') and (x_Family == 'Unassigned') and (x_Genus == 'Unassigned')) or
    (pd.isnull(x_VC)):
        sub_df = demovir_df[demovir_df['Sequence_ID'] == x_Genome]
        if len(sub_df) > 0:
            order = sub_df['Order'].iloc[0]
            family = sub_df['Family'].iloc[0]
            tool = 'demovir'
        else:
            order = x_Order
            family = x_Family

```

```

        tool = x_taxa_tool + ', demovir'
else:
    order = x_Order
    family = x_Family
    tool = x_taxa_tool + ', demovir'
return pd.Series([order, family, tool])

# import demovir dataframe
demovir_df = pd.read_csv(argv[2], sep='\t')

# iterate through contig database and pull out demovir assignment if vcontact2 gave 'undetermined'
contig_df[['Order', 'Family', 'taxa_tool']] = contig_df.apply(lambda x: update_demovir_taxa(x['VC'],
x['Genome'], x['Order'], x['Family'], x['Genus'], x['taxa_tool'], demovir_df), axis = 1)

# replace all taxa nan values with 'Undetermined'
for i in ['VC', 'Kingdom', 'Phylum', 'Class', 'Order', 'Family', 'Genus']:
    contig_df[i] = contig_df[i].fillna('Unassigned')

#####

##### process bacphlip table #####

# import bacphlip df
bacphlip_df = pd.read_csv(argv[3], sep = '\t')

# rename bacphlip columns
bacphlip_df.columns = ['Genome', 'bacphlip_virulent', 'bacphlip_temperate', 'bacphlip_result']

# merge contig_df with bacphlip df
contig_df = contig_df.merge(bacphlip_df, on='Genome', how='left')

#####

```

```

##### process iphop table #####

# import iphop dataframe
iphop_df = pd.read_csv(argv[4])

# determine if contigs are generalists or specialists (based on if they infect more than one taxa)
iphop_contig_virus_count = pd.DataFrame(iphop_df['Virus'].value_counts()).reset_index()
iphop_contig_virus_count.columns = ['Genome', 'host_count']
iphop_contig_virus_count['gen_v_spec'] = iphop_contig_virus_count.apply(lambda x: 'Generalist' if
x['host_count'] > 1 else 'Specialist', axis=1)

# merge general or specialist decisions with contig_df
contig_df = contig_df.merge(iphop_contig_virus_count, on='Genome', how='left')

# replace nan's
contig_df['gen_v_spec'] = contig_df['gen_v_spec'].fillna('Undetermined')

# break host genus contig to specific taxa
iphop_df[['host_domain', 'host_phylum', 'host_clade', 'host_order', 'host_family', 'host_genus']] =
iphop_df['Host genus'].str.split(';', 5, expand=True)

# keep only useful contigs
iphop_df = iphop_df[['Virus', 'host_domain', 'host_phylum', 'host_clade', 'host_order', 'host_family',
'host_genus']]

# rename columns
iphop_df.columns = ['Genome', 'host_domain', 'host_phylum', 'host_clade', 'host_order', 'host_family',
'host_genus']

# merge this with contig_df
contig_df = contig_df.merge(iphop_df, on='Genome', how='left')

```

```
# fill na's
for i in ['host_domain', 'host_phylum', 'host_clade', 'host_order', 'host_family', 'host_genus']:
    contig_df[i] = contig_df[i].fillna(i.split('host_-')[0] + '__Undetermined')
```

```
#####
```

```
##### Write the master table to file #####
```

```
contig_df.to_csv(argv[5], sep = '\t', index=False)
```

```
#####
```

Get_good_viral_contigs_v1

```
import pandas as pd
```

```
from sys import argv
```

```
import numpy as np
```

```
from Bio import SeqIO
```

```
from collections import Counter
```

```
# {input.orfs} {input.nucl} {input.virsorter} {input.dvf}
```

```
# input variable
```

```
# argv[1] = path to file with list of good contigs from proteins searches
```

```
# argv[2] = path to file with list of good contigs from nucl searches
```

```
# argv[3] = path to virsorter score file
```

```
# argv[4] = path to dvf score file
```

```
# argv[5] = path to circular contigs file
```

```
# argv[6] = path to nr contigs fasta
```

```
# argv[7] = output file path
```

```
# collect list of good contigs from the filtered protein blast output
```

```

prot_contig_list = []
with open(argv[1]) as prot:
    for contig in prot:
        contig = contig.strip()
        prot_contig_list.append(contig)

# collect list of good contigs from the filtered nucl blast output
nucl_contig_list = []
with open(argv[2]) as nucl:
    for contig in nucl:
        contig = contig.strip()
        nucl_contig_list.append(contig)

# collect and filter list of good contigs from virsorter output

# load virsorter input
virsorter = pd.read_csv(argv[3], sep='\t')

# filter virsorter contigs to keep only contigs with score ≥0.9 or score of ≥0.7 with at least one viral
hallmark protein-coding gene present
virsorter = virsorter[(virsorter['max_score'] >= 0.9) | ((virsorter['max_score'] >= 0.7) &
(virsorter['hallmark'] >=1))].reset_index(drop=True)

# extract contig name from seqname column of virsorter table
virsorter['qseqid'] = virsorter['seqname'].str.split('|').str[0]

# get list of the virsorter contigs that passed filtering steps above
virsorter_contig_list = list(virsorter['qseqid'].unique())

```

```

# import dvf output table
dvf = pd.read_csv(argv[4], sep='\t')

# filter dvf table to only keep contigs with pvalue < 0.05
dvf = dvf[dvf['pvalue'] < 0.05]

# get list of dvf contigs that passed filtering
dvf_contig_list = list(dvf['name'].unique())

# read VRCA circular fasta and make into list
circular_list = []
for record in SeqIO.parse(argv[5], 'fasta'):
    circular_list.append(record.id)

# combine all the lists of contigs passing the filters for each method
good_contigs = prot_contig_list + nucl_contig_list + virsorter_contig_list + dvf_contig_list + circular_list

# remove redundancy from the good contigs list to keep only each contig name only once
good_contigs = list(set(good_contigs))

# extract contigs passing screening filters from the nr contig db
keep_contigs = []
for record in SeqIO.parse(argv[6], 'fasta'):
    if record.id in good_contigs:
        keep_contigs.append(record)

# output the contigs to keep in fasta format
SeqIO.write(keep_contigs,argv[7],'fasta')

Fix_gbm_format
from sys import argv

```

```

import pandas as pd

gbms = {'gbm':[], 'function':[], 'kos':[]}

with open(str(snakemake.input), 'r') as f:

    data = f.read()
    data = data.replace('\n', '\t')
    lines = data.split('///')
    print(lines)

    for line in lines:
        if line != '\t':
            line = line.split('\t')
            line = [x for x in line if x != ""]
            kos = ';;'.join([x for item in line[2:] for x in item.split(',')])

            gbms['gbm'].append(line[0])
            gbms['function'].append(line[1])
            gbms['kos'].append(kos)

df = pd.DataFrame.from_dict(gbms)

df.to_csv(str(snakemake.output), sep='\t', index=False)

```

Filter_prot_hits_v1

```

import pandas as pd
from sys import argv
import numpy as np
from Bio import SeqIO
from collections import Counter

```

```
# input variable
# argv[1] = all contigs prodigal faa
# argv[2] = blast vs refseq viral protein filepath
# argv[3] = hmm vs phrogs database filepath
# argv[4] = hmm vs inovirus database filepath
# argv[5] = output file path

##### process blast vs refseq #####

# get blast input as pandas dataframe
df = pd.read_csv(argv[2], sep = '\t', names=['qseqid', 'sseqid', 'pident', 'length', 'mismatch', 'gapopen',
'qstart', 'qend', 'qlen', 'sstart', 'send', 'slen', 'evalue', 'bitscore'])

# get list of orfs hit from blast table
all_orfs_hit = list(df['qseqid'].unique())

#####

##### process hmm vs phrogs #####

# get hmm input as pandas dataframe
df = pd.read_csv(argv[3],delim_whitespace=True, comment='#', names = ['sseqid', 'qseqid'],
usecols=[0,2])

# append hmm orfs to list of orfs hit
all_orfs_hit += list(df['qseqid'].unique())

#####

##### process hmm vs inovirus #####
```

```

# get hmm input as pandas dataframe
df = pd.read_csv(argv[4],delim_whitespace=True, comment='#', names = ['sseqid', 'qseqid'],
usecols=[0,2])

# append hmm orfs to list of orfs hit
all_orfs_hit += list(df['qseqid'].unique())

#####

##### identify contigs passing filtering #####

# get overall unique orf names hit
unique_orfs_hit = list(set(all_orfs_hit))

# convert orf names to contig name
unique_orfs_hit = ['_'.join(x.split('_')[:-1]) for x in unique_orfs_hit]

# count the times a contig name appears in the list and export that as a dataframe (i.e. contig name appears
2x = hit orf count of 2)
unique_orfs_hit = pd.DataFrame.from_dict(Counter(unique_orfs_hit), orient='index').reset_index()

# fix column names
unique_orfs_hit.columns = ['contig', 'hit_orf_count']

# create empty list to hold contig name for computing total orf counts
contig_orf_count = []

# iterate through each orf in faa and add the associated contig name a list
for record in SeqIO.parse(argv[1], 'fasta'):
    contig_orf_count.append('_'.join(record.id.split('_')[:-1]))

```

```
# count the times a contig name appears in the list and export that as a dataframe (i.e. contig name appears
2x = total orf count of 2)
```

```
contig_orf_count = pd.DataFrame.from_dict(Counter(contig_orf_count), orient='index').reset_index()
```

```
# fix column names
```

```
contig_orf_count.columns = ['contig', 'orf_count']
```

```
# combine the hit orf count df and total orf counts dfs
```

```
contig_orf_count = contig_orf_count.merge(unique_orfs_hit, on='contig')
```

```
# remove any contigs that have <= 2 orfs unless both orfs have been hit, and those where less than 3 orfs
have been hit or orfs hit account for < 50% of the contig
```

```
contig_orf_count = contig_orf_count[(contig_orf_count['orf_count'] > 2) | ((contig_orf_count['orf_count']
== 2) & (contig_orf_count['hit_orf_count'] == 2))]
```

```
# remove any contigs that have less than 2 orf hits where both orfs have not been hit, and any contigs
with less than 3 orfs hit or those where 3 or more have been hit but that this accounts for less than 50% of
their total orf count
```

```
contig_orf_count = contig_orf_count[(
    (
        (contig_orf_count['orf_count'] == 2) &
        (contig_orf_count['hit_orf_count'] == 2)
    ) |
    (
        (contig_orf_count['hit_orf_count'] >= 3) &
        (contig_orf_count['hit_orf_count'] >= contig_orf_count['orf_count'] * 0.5)
    )
)]
```

```
# make a contig names that pass that filter
```

```
good_contigs = list(set(contig_orf_count['contig']))
```

```
#####
```

```
##### write output to file #####
```

```
# write list of the good contigs to file
```

```
with open(argv[5], 'w') as outfile:
```

```
    for contig in good_contigs:
```

```
        outfile.write('{}\n'.format(contig))
```

```
#####
```

filter_nucl_blast_hits_v1

```
import pandas as pd
```

```
from sys import argv
```

```
import numpy as np
```

```
import multiprocessing
```

```
from functools import partial
```

```
# input variable
```

```
# argv[1] = pid cut off as %
```

```
# argv[2] = length cut off as proportion i.e. 90% = 0.9
```

```
# argv[3] = output file path
```

```
# argv[4] = thread count
```

```
# argv[5] onward = blast file path
```

```
def split_df_for_multiproc(df, threads):
```

```
    chunk_size = int(len(df['qseqid'].unique())/threads)
```

```
    if chunk_size == 0:
```

```
        chunk_size = 1
```

```
    chunk_names = [list(df['qseqid'].unique())[i:i + chunk_size] for i in range(0, len(df['qseqid'].unique()),  
chunk_size)]
```

```
    chunks = [df[df['qseqid'].isin(chunk)] for chunk in chunk_names]
```

```
    pool = multiprocessing.Pool(processes=threads)
```

```

return chunks, pool

def multiprocessing_check_total_bases_covered(df):
    new_df = {'qseqid':[], 'qlen':[], 'covered_base_length': []}
    for i in df['qseqid'].unique():
        ranges = 0
        ranges = set()
        for index, row in df[df['qseqid'] == i].iterrows():
            start = min([row['qstart'], row['qend']])
            end = max([row['qstart'], row['qend']])
            ranges.update(range(start - 1 , end))
        new_df['qseqid'].append(i)
        new_df['qlen'].append(row['qlen'])
        new_df['covered_base_length'].append(len(ranges)) # issue around here where simple table contains
some with value > 1
    new_df = pd.DataFrame.from_dict(new_df)
    return new_df

# create empty list to hold good contigs
good_contigs = []

# iterate over each of the blast files
for i in argv[5:]:

    # convert blast input to pandas dataframe
    df = pd.read_csv(i, sep = '\t', names=['qseqid', 'sseqid', 'pident', 'length', 'mismatch', 'gapopen', 'qstart',
'qend', 'qlen', 'sstart', 'send', 'slen', 'evalue', 'bitscore', 'staxids', 'stitle'])

    # filter df to remove matches that have less than argv[1] % matching identity
    df = df[df['pident'] >= float(argv[1])]

    # append this df to list of others that pass given threshold

```

```

    good_contigs.append(df)

# concatenate list of dataframe into one big dataframe
good_contigs = pd.concat(good_contigs).reset_index(drop=True)

# split df ahead of multiprocessing
chunks, pool = split_df_for_multiproc(good_contigs, int(argv[4]))

# look for overall coverage across databases
good_contigs = pd.concat(pool.map(partial(multiprocess_check_total_bases_covered),
chunks)).reset_index(drop=True)

# calculate proportion of contig covered by hits
good_contigs['prop_covered'] = good_contigs['covered_base_length'] / good_contigs['qlen']
print(good_contigs)

# filter contigs to keep only those with argv[2] proportion of the contig covered by blast hits
good_contigs = good_contigs[good_contigs['prop_covered'] >= float(argv[2])].reset_index(drop=True)

# convert passing contigs to list of contig names
good_contigs = list(good_contigs['qseqid'].unique())

# write list of accessions to keep to file
with open(argv[3], 'w') as outfile:
    for contig in good_contigs:
        outfile.write('{}\n'.format(contig))

```

Filter_contig_blast_hits_v1

```

import pandas as pd
from sys import argv
from Bio import SeqIO
import numpy as np

```

```

import multiprocessing
from functools import partial

# input variable
# argv[1] = blast file path
# argv[2] = blasted fasta file path
# argv[3] = output file path
# argv[4] = pid cut off as %
# argv[5] = length cut off as proportion i.e. 90% = 0.9
# argv[6] = no. threads to use

def split_df_for_multiproc(df, threads):
    chunk_size = int(len(df['qseqid'].unique())/threads)
    if chunk_size == 0:
        chunk_size = 1
    chunk_names = [list(df['qseqid'].unique())[i:i + chunk_size] for i in range(0, len(df['qseqid'].unique()),
chunk_size)]
    chunks = [df[df['qseqid'].isin(chunk)] for chunk in chunk_names]
    pool = multiprocessing.Pool(processes=threads)
    return chunks, pool

def multiprocess_check_total_bases_covered(df):
    new_df = {'qseqid': [], 'sseqid': [], 'qlen': [], 'slen': [], 'covered_base_length': []}
    for i in df['combo'].unique():
        ranges = 0
        ranges = set()
        for index, row in df[df['combo'] == i].iterrows():
            start = min([row['qstart'], row['qend']])
            end = max([row['qstart'], row['qend']])
            ranges.update(range(start - 1, end))
        new_df['qseqid'].append(row['qseqid'])
        new_df['sseqid'].append(row['sseqid'])

```

```

    new_df['qlen'].append(row['qlen'])
    new_df['slen'].append(row['slen'])
    new_df['covered_base_length'].append(len(ranges)) # issue around here where simple table contains
some with value > 1
    new_df = pd.DataFrame.from_dict(new_df)
    return new_df

# import blast table

df = pd.read_csv(argv[1], sep = '\t', names=['qseqid', 'sseqid', 'pident', 'length', 'mismatch', 'gapopen',
'qstart', 'qend', 'qlen', 'sstart', 'send', 'slen', 'eval', 'bitscore'])

# drop all self blasting results

df = df[df['qseqid'] != df['sseqid']]

# do initial filter to remove any matches that are < X% id

df = df[df['pident'] >= float(argv[4])].reset_index(drop=True)

# add column to simplify qseqid sseqid checking

df['combo'] = df['qseqid'] + '~' + df['sseqid']

# make temp df that hold qseqid sseqid pairs that appear more than once

multi_df = df[df.groupby('combo')['combo'].transform('size') > 1].reset_index(drop=True)

# remove those multi ones from main df

df = df[df.groupby('combo')['combo'].transform('size') == 1].reset_index(drop=True)

```

```

# add covered_base_length column to main df

df['covered_base_length'] = df.apply(lambda x: max([x['qstart'], x['qend']]) - min([x['qstart'], x['qend']]) +
1, axis = 1)

# split multi df ahead of multi thread processing

chunks, pool = split_df_for_multiproc(multi_df, int(argv[6])) # may need to modify this to x names per
chunk as dont want one name to be split over multiple threads

# for each qseqid match check the total bases covered by the each sseqid result (in case some hits are
given as multiple hits by blastout)

multi_df = pd.concat(pool.map(partial(multiprocess_check_total_bases_covered),
chunks)).reset_index(drop=True)

# give single hit df the same number of columns as multi

df = df[['qseqid', 'sseqid', 'qlen', 'slen', 'covered_base_length']]

# merge the two dfs

df = pd.concat([df, multi_df]).reset_index(drop=True)

# calculate proportion of contig covered by hit

df['hit_prop'] = df['covered_base_length'] / df['qlen']

# filter to only keep contigs with over X % coverage

df = df[df['hit_prop'] >= float(argv[5])].reset_index(drop=True)

# make list of qseqids where contigs qlen were smaller than slen

```

```

remove_contigs = list(df['qseqid'][df['qlen'] < df['slen']].unique())

# make list of qseqids where contigs qlen is same as slen

same = df[(df['qlen'] == df['slen']) & ((~df['qseqid'].isin(remove_contigs)) &
(~df['sseqid'].isin(remove_contigs)))]

# add everything but the first instance of a unique qseqid to the smaller_hit list

for index, row in same.iterrows():
    if not row['qseqid'] in remove_contigs:
        remove_contigs.append(row['sseqid'])

# create list of seq records that aren't in the remove contigs list (i.e. the good contigs we want)

keep_contigs = []
for record in SeqIO.parse(argv[2], 'fasta'):
    if record.id not in remove_contigs:
        record.description = "
        record.name = "
        keep_contigs.append(record)

# output the contigs to keep in fasta format

SeqIO.write(keep_contigs,argv[3],'fasta')

```

Extract_faa

```

from Bio import SeqIO
from sys import argv
import pandas as pd

```

```
# Input: faa file
fasta_file = argv[1]

# Input: table containing good ids
table_file = argv[2]

# Output: faa of good ids
out_file = argv[3]

# Read in table
table = pd.read_csv(table_file, sep='\t')

# Get good ids
good_ids = table['name'].tolist()

# create empty list to hold good records
good_records = []

# Read in fasta file
for record in SeqIO.parse(fasta_file, "fasta"):
    # Check if id is in good ids
    if '_'.join(record.id.split('_')[:-1]) in good_ids:
        # Add to good records
        good_records.append(record)

# Write out good records
SeqIO.write(good_records, out_file, "fasta")

Get_count_table
from sys import argv
from glob import glob
```

```

import pandas as pd

# argv[1] = path to file containing total read counts per sample
# argv[2] = path to folder containing processed mpileup files
# argv[3] = path to output the processed and total-sum normalised counts to as long table
# argv[4] = path to the total-sum normalised read counts in the style of an otu table to

# import total number of reads in the samples
total_reads_count_df = pd.read_csv(argv[1], sep='\t', names=['sample', 'read_no'])

# import all mpileup files and use to create new pandas dataframe
mpileup_df = []
for i in glob(argv[2] + '/*_mpileup_cov.tsv'):
    sub_df = pd.read_csv(i, sep='\t')
    sub_df['sample'] = i.split('_mpileup_cov.tsv')[0].split('/')[-1]
    mpileup_df.append(sub_df)
mpileup_df = pd.concat(mpileup_df).reset_index(drop=True)

# process mpileup df to set coverages to 0 for any contig that less than 75% of its length has been covered
by at least 1x coverage
mpileup_df['width_adjusted_counts'] = mpileup_df.apply(lambda x: 0 if x['proportion'] < 0.75 else
x['no_mapped_reads'], axis=1)

# normalise read counts by contig length (i.e. counts/base)
mpileup_df['length_normalised_counts'] = mpileup_df['width_adjusted_counts'] / mpileup_df['length']

# total-sum normalise each read set by dividing the normalised reads by the total number of quality
filtered reads in the sample (could be multiprocessed)
mpileup_df['total-sum_normalised'] = mpileup_df.apply(lambda x:
(x['length_normalised_counts']/total_reads_count_df['read_no'])[total_reads_count_df['sample'] ==
x['sample']].iloc[0]), axis=1)

# replace any nan values in the total-sum normalised column with 0s

```

```
mpileup_df['total-sum_normalised'] = mpileup_df['total-sum_normalised'].fillna(0)
```

```
# output the mpileup_df to a file
```

```
mpileup_df.to_csv(argv[3], sep = '\t', index = False)
```

```
# output total-sum_normalised otu table
```

```
mpileup_df.pivot(index='name', columns='sample', values='total-sum_normalised').to_csv(argv[4], sep = '\t')
```

Process_mpileup_v1

```
import pandas as pd
```

```
from sys import argv
```

```
from Bio import SeqIO
```

```
# argv[1] = a single mapping mpileup file
```

```
# argv[2] = the corresponding idxstats file
```

```
# argv[3] = fasta file containing contigs that were mapped to
```

```
# argv[4] = output file path
```

```
# import pileup output and idxstats output
```

```
pileup = pd.read_csv(argv[1], sep='\t', names = ['name', 'pos', 'n', 'number_reads_cov', 'base', 'quality'])
```

```
idxstats = pd.read_csv(argv[2], sep='\t', names = ['name', 'length', 'no_mapped_reads', 'no_unmapped_reads'])
```

```
# remove any rows with 0 read coverage from pileup
```

```
pileup = pileup[pileup['number_reads_cov'] > 0]
```

```
# count number of rows containing a given contigs name in pileup (will be one per base covered) and overwrite pileup df
```

```
pileup = pd.DataFrame(pileup['name'].value_counts()).reset_index()
```

```

# have contingency in the even that the dataframe is empty
if len(pileup) == 0:
    pileup = pd.DataFrame(columns=['A', 'B'])

# rename the columns of the counted pileup
pileup.columns = ['name', 'covered_bases']

# drop unnecessary columns from idxstats df
idxstats = idxstats[['name', 'length', 'no_mapped_reads']]

# join pileup and idxstats
pileup = pileup.merge(idxstats, on='name').reset_index(drop=True)

# calculate the proportion of bases in the contig with at least 1x coverages
pileup['proportion'] = pileup['covered_bases']/pileup['length']

# get list of contigs add hit by reads
found = pileup['name'].unique()

# create empty dataframe to house contigs that had no mapped reads
missing = {'name': [], 'covered_bases': [], 'length': [], 'no_mapped_reads': [], 'proportion': []}

# parse the contig fasta to collect see all contig names and add those missing from the 'found' list to the
'missing' dataframe and set the values of these to 0
for record in SeqIO.parse(argv[3], 'fasta'):
    if record.id not in found:
        missing['name'].append(record.id)
        missing['covered_bases'].append(0)
        missing['length'].append(len(record.seq))
        missing['no_mapped_reads'].append(0)
        missing['proportion'].append(0.0)
missing = pd.DataFrame.from_dict(missing)

```

```
# join the 'missing' dataframe to the one pileup results
```

```
pileup = pd.concat([pileup, missing])
```

```
# write table to to file
```

```
pileup.to_csv(argv[4], sep='\t', index=False, header=True)
```

Epifluorescent microscopy virus-like particle counts

```
# coding=utf-8
```

```
# usage
```

```
# python count_circles_in_folders.py /path/to/your/images/
```

```
#
```

```
#
```

```
# assumes that your images are in a folder structure e.g.
```

```
# folder
```

```
# - folder
```

```
#   - image
```

```
#   - image
```

```
# - folder
```

```
#   - image
```

```
import NumPy as np
```

```
import cv2
```

```
import os, sys
```

```
def process_image(image_path):
```

```
    image = cv2.imread(image_path)
```

```
    output = image.copy()
```

```
    gray2 = image.copy()
```

```
    gray = cv2.cvtColor(image, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
```

```
    rows,cols,_ = image.shape
```

```
    def count_average(image, i, j, area=20):
```

```
        total = 0
```

```
        pixels = 0
```

```
        for x in range(i - area, i + area):
```

```
            for y in range(j - area, j + area):
```

```
                try:
```

```
                    k = image[x, y]
```

```
                except:
```

```
                    continue
```

```
            total += k
```

```
            pixels += 1
```

```

        return total / pixels

total = 0

for i in range(rows):
    for j in range(cols):
        k = gray[i,j]

        total += k

        if gray[i,j] > count_average(gray, i, j, 5) + 7:
            gray2[i,j] = 255
        else:
            gray2[i,j] = 0

average = total / (rows * cols)

print("Avg: {}".format(average))

gray2 = cv2.cvtColor(gray2, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)

th, threshed = cv2.threshold(gray2, average * 1.6,
255,cv2.THRESH_BINARY_INV|cv2.ADAPTIVE_THRESH_GAUSSIAN_C)

cnts = cv2.findContours(threshed, cv2.RETR_TREE, cv2.CHAIN_APPROX_SIMPLE)[-2]

s1 = 2.0
s2 = 60.0
xcnts = []

for cnt in cnts:
    if s1 < cv2.contourArea(cnt) < s2:
        xcnts.append(cnt)

        cv2.drawContours(output, cnt, 0, (0,0,255), len(cnt)//2)

return len(xcnts), np.hstack([image, output])

new_root = './output/'

for root, dirs, files in sorted(os.walk(sys.argv[1])):
    for file in files:
        if not file.endswith('.tif'):
            continue

        output_path = os.path.join(new_root, root.replace(sys.argv[1], ""))

        if not os.path.exists(output_path):
            os.makedirs(output_path)

        if os.path.exists(os.path.join(output_path, file)):
            continue

        count, final_image = process_image(os.path.join(root, file))

```

```
cv2.imwrite(os.path.join(output_path, file), final_image)
print(os.path.join(output_path, file), count)
```